

Supplementary material: Semantic Augmentation on Motion Manifold for Single-Stream Unsupervised Action Recognition

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1 Exponential Mapping and Logarithmic Mapping

Exponential mapping and logarithmic mapping on the sphere are well-defined. By utilizing exponential mapping and logarithmic mapping, it is possible to achieve the conversion between points in the tangent space and points on the sphere. The exponential map of \mathbb{S}^2 denotes as:

$$\exp_{s_i}(\nu) = \cos(\|\nu\|)s_i + \frac{\sin(\|\nu\|)}{\|\nu\|}\nu$$

The logarithm map of \mathbb{S}^2 is

$$\log_{s_i}(s_j) = \frac{\rho}{\sin(\rho)}(s_j - s_i \cos(\rho)),$$

and the parallel transport from s_i to s_j on \mathbb{S}^2 is denoted as:

$$pt_{s_i \rightarrow s_j}(\nu) = \nu - \frac{\langle s_j, \nu \rangle}{1 + \cos(\rho)}(s_i + s_j),$$

where $s_i, s_j \in \mathbb{S}^2$, $\nu \in T_{s_i}\mathbb{S}^2$, $\nu' \in T_{s_j}\mathbb{S}^2$, ρ is the Riemannian distance in \mathbb{S}^2 , and $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$ is the Euclidean inner product. The exponential map **Exp**, logarithm map **Log** and parallel transport **Pt** of \mathcal{P} are respectively denoted as:

$$\mathbf{Exp}_c(V) = (\exp_{s_1}(\nu_1), \dots, \exp_{s_{K-1}}(\nu_{K-1}))$$

$$\mathbf{Log}_c(c') = (\log_{s_1}(s'_1), \dots, \log_{s_{K-1}}(s'_{K-1}))$$

$$\mathbf{Pt}_{c \rightarrow c'}(V) = (pt_{s_1 \rightarrow s'_1}(\nu_1), \dots, pt_{s_{K-1} \rightarrow s'_{K-1}}(\nu_{K-1}))$$

where $c, c' \in \mathcal{P}$, $V \in T_c\mathcal{P}$, and $s_k, s'_k \in \mathbb{S}_k^2$.

2 Normal Augmentations \mathcal{L}_n

For the normal augmentation, we follow the approach described in [3, 2, 1]. We employed two spatial augmentation methods, Pose Augmentation and Joint Jittering, and a temporal augmentation method Temporal Crop-resize.

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Pose Augmentation This augmentation is a linear transformation on the spatial dimension. The transformation matrix is:

$$A_{PA} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & a_1 & a_2 \\ a_3 & 1 & a_4 \\ a_5 & a_6 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

where a_1, \dots, a_6 are sampled randomly from $[-1, 1]$. Then the sequence is multiplied by the transformation matrix A on the channel dimension.

Joint Jittering This augmentation is a linear transformation on the spatial dimension. The transformation matrix is:

$$A_{JJ} = \begin{bmatrix} a_1 & a_2 & a_3 \\ a_4 & a_5 & a_6 \\ a_7 & a_8 & a_9 \end{bmatrix}$$

where a_1, \dots, a_9 are sampled randomly from $[-1, 1]$. Randomly select 15 joints from a total of 25 joints for linear transformation.

Temporal Crop-resize The Temporal Crop-resize originated from image classification tasks. For time series data, we divide the actions into different segments by performing random cropping $X[T_{start} : T_{start} + L_{ratio}]$, where L_{ratio} is first randomly sampled from distribution $[0.1, 1]$. Then the sub-sequence $X[T_{start} : T_{start} + L_{ratio}]$ is then re-sampled to a fixed length (300 frames) by symmetrically padding some frames to the sequence.

3 Algorithm

We provide the discrete algorithm of TSRVF transformation for an action sequence on \mathcal{P} .

Algorithm 1 TSRVF transformation

Input: $[c_1, c_2, \dots, c_T]$

Output: $[\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_{T-1}]$

1: **for** $i=1; i \leq T-1; i++$ **do**

2: $\xi_i = \mathbf{Log}_{c_i} c_{i+1}$

3: $\xi_i = \mathbf{Pt}_{c_i \rightarrow c_0} \xi_i$

4: $\alpha_i = \frac{\xi_i}{\sqrt{\|\xi_i\|_2}}$

5: **end for**

6: **return** $[\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_{T-1}]$

Algorithm 2 Inverse TSRVF transformation

Input: $[\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_{T-1}]$, c_0 **Output:** $[c_1, c_2, \dots, c_T]$

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1: for  $i=1; i \leq T-1; i++$  do  
2:    $\xi_i = \alpha_i / \|\alpha_i\|_2$   
3:    $\xi_i = \text{Pt}_{c_0 \rightarrow c_{i-1}} \xi_i$   
4:    $c_i = \text{Exp}_{c_{i-1}} \xi_i$   
5: end for  
6: return  $[c_1, c_2, \dots, c_T]$ 
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References

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